

**q -MULTIPARAMETER-BERNOULLI POLYNOMIALS AND
 q -MULTIPARAMETER-CAUCHY POLYNOMIALS BY JACKSON'S
 INTEGRALS**

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Abstract

We define q -multiparameter-Bernoulli polynomials and q -multiparameter-Cauchy polynomials by using Jackson's integrals, which generalize the previously known numbers, including poly-Bernoulli $B_n^{(k)}$ and the poly-Cauchy numbers of the first kind $c_n^{(k)}$ and of the second kind $\widehat{c}_n^{(k)}$. We investigate their properties connected with multiparameter Stirling numbers which generalize the original Stirling numbers. We also give the relations between q -multiparameter-Bernoulli polynomials and q -multiparameter-Cauchy polynomials.

1. Introduction

Let n and k be integers with $n \geq 0$, and let $L = (l_1, \dots, l_k)$ be a k -tuple of real numbers with $\ell := l_1 \cdots l_k \neq 0$ and $A = (\alpha_0, \alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_{n-1})$ be a n -tuple of real numbers. Let q be a real number with $0 \leq q < 1$.

Jackson's q -derivative with $0 < q < 1$ (see e.g., [1, (10.2.3)], [12]) is defined by

$$D_q f = \frac{d_q f}{d_q x} = \frac{f(x) - f(qx)}{(1-q)x}$$

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and Jackson's q -integral ([1, (10.1.3)], [12]) is defined by

$$\int_0^x f(t) d_q t = (1 - q)x \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} f(q^n x) q^n.$$

The Jackson integral gives a unique q -antiderivative within a certain class of functions. In particular, when $f(x) = x^m$ for some nonnegative integer m , then

$$D_q f = \frac{x^m - q^m x^m}{(1 - q)x} = [m]_q x^{m-1}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^x t^m d_q t &= (1 - q)x \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} q^{mn} x^m q^n \\ &= (1 - q)x^{m+1} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} q^{n(m+1)} = \frac{x^{m+1}}{[m+1]_q}. \end{aligned}$$

Here,

$$[x]_q = \frac{1 - q^x}{1 - q}$$

is the q -number with $[0]_q = 0$ (see e.g. [1, (10.2.3)], [12]). Note that $\lim_{q \rightarrow 1} [x]_q = x$.

Define *poly-Bernoulli polynomials* $B_{n,\rho,q}^{(k)}(z)$ with a parameter ρ by

$$\frac{\rho}{1 - e^{-\rho t}} \text{Li}_{k,q} \left(\frac{1 - e^{-\rho t}}{\rho} \right) e^{-tz} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_{n,\rho,q}^{(k)}(z) \frac{t^n}{n!}, \tag{1}$$

where $\text{Li}_{k,q}(z)$ is the q -polylogarithm function (see [16]) defined by

$$\text{Li}_{k,q}(z) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{z^n}{[n]_q^k}.$$

Notice that

$$\lim_{q \rightarrow 1} B_{n,\rho,q}^{(k)}(z) = B_{n,\rho}^{(k)}(z),$$

which is the poly-Bernoulli polynomial with a ρ parameter (see [6]), and

$$\lim_{q \rightarrow 1} \text{Li}_{k,q}(z) = \text{Li}_k(z),$$

which is the ordinary polylogarithm function, defined by

$$\text{Li}_k(z) = \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{z^m}{m^k}. \tag{2}$$

In addition, when $z = 0$, $B_{n,\rho}^{(k)}(0) = B_{n,\rho}^{(k)}$ is the poly-Bernoulli number with a ρ parameter. When $z = 0$ and $\rho = 1$, $B_{n,1}^{(k)}(0) = B_n^{(k)}$ is the *poly-Bernoulli number* (see [15]) defined by

$$\frac{\text{Li}_k(1 - e^{-t})}{1 - e^{-t}} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_n^{(k)} \frac{t^n}{n!}. \tag{3}$$

The poly-Bernoulli numbers are expressed as special values at negative arguments of certain combinations of multiple zeta values. The poly-Bernoulli numbers can be expressed in terms of the Stirling numbers of the second kind.

$$B_n^{(k)} = \sum_{m=0}^n \frac{(-1)^{n-m} m! S_2(n, m)}{(m + 1)^k} \quad (n \geq 0, k \geq 1)$$

([15, Theorem 1]), where $S_2(n, m)$ is the Stirling number of the second kind, see [7], determined by the falling factorial:

$$x^n = \sum_{m=0}^n S_2(n, m) x(x - 1) \cdots (x - m + 1).$$

The poly-Bernoulli numbers are extended to the poly-Bernoulli polynomials (see [3, 8]) and to the special multi-poly-Bernoulli numbers (see [11]). The Bernoulli polynomials occur in the study of many special functions and in particular the Riemann zeta function and the Hurwitz zeta function. They are an Appell sequence, i.e., a Sheffer sequence for the ordinary derivative operator.

Define the q -multiparameter-poly-Cauchy polynomials of the first kind $c_{n,L,A,q}^{(k)}(z)$ by

$$c_{n,L,A,q}^{(k)}(z) = \int_0^{l_1} \cdots \int_0^{l_k} (x_1 \cdots x_k - \alpha_0 - z) \cdots (x_1 \cdots x_k - \alpha_{n-1} - z) d_q x_1 \cdots d_q x_k. \tag{4}$$

Notice that

$$\lim_{q \rightarrow 1} c_{n,L,A,q}^{(k)}(z) = c_{n,L,A}^{(k)}(z),$$

which are the multiparameter-poly-Cauchy polynomials of the first kind. The idea of dealing with multiparameters $\alpha_0, \alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_{n-1}$ instead of $0, 1, \dots, n - 1$ has already been considered in [25]. Namely, If $l_1 = \cdots = l_k = 1$ and $z = 0$, the number $c_{n,(1,\dots,1),A}^{(k)} = c_{n,A}^{(k)}$ has been studied to prove the convexity. It has been proven that $c_{n,A}^{(k)}$ is log-convex, satisfying $(c_{n,A}^{(k)})^2 - c_{n-1,A}^{(k)} c_{n+1,A}^{(k)} \leq 0$.

In addition, if $\alpha_i = i\rho$ ($i = 0, 1, \dots, n - 1$), then the number $c_{n,A}^{(k)}$ is reduced to the poly-Cauchy numbers of the first kind with a parameter ρ (see [19]). Furthermore, if $\rho = 1$, then the number $c_{n,A}^{(k)}$ is reduced to the poly-Cauchy number $c_n^{(k)}$ (see [18]). If $k = 1$, then $c_n^{(1)} = c_n$ is the classical Cauchy number (see [7, 27]). The

number $c_n/n!$ is sometimes referred to as the Bernoulli number of the second kind (see [4, 13, 28]).

The poly-Cauchy numbers have been considered as analogues of the poly-Bernoulli numbers $B_n^{(k)}$. The poly-Cauchy numbers of the first kind, $c_n^{(k)}$, can be expressed in terms of the Stirling numbers of the first kind:

$$c_n^{(k)} = \sum_{m=0}^n \frac{(-1)^{n-m} S_1(n, m)}{(m+1)^k} \quad (n \geq 0, k \geq 1)$$

([18, Theorem 1]), where $S_1(n, m)$ is the (unsigned) Stirling number of the first kind (see [7]), determined by the rising factorial:

$$x(x+1) \cdots (x+n-1) = \sum_{m=0}^n S_1(n, m)x^m. \tag{5}$$

Similarly, define the q -multiparameter-poly-Cauchy polynomials of the second kind $\widehat{c}_{n,L,A,q}^{(k)}(z)$ by

$$\begin{aligned} &\widehat{c}_{n,L,A,q}^{(k)}(z) \\ &= \int_0^{l_1} \cdots \int_0^{l_k} (-x_1 \cdots x_k - \alpha_0 + z) \cdots (-x_1 \cdots x_k - \alpha_{n-1} + z) d_q x_1 \cdots d_q x_k. \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

If $q \rightarrow 1$, $l_1 = \cdots = l_k = 1$, $\alpha_i = i\rho$ ($i = 0, 1, \dots, n-1$) and $z = 0$, the number $\widehat{c}_{n,A}^{(k)}$ is reduced to the poly-Cauchy numbers of the second kind with a parameter ρ (see [19]). Furthermore, if $\rho = 1$, then the number $\widehat{c}_{n,A}^{(k)}$ is reduced to the poly-Cauchy numbers of the second kind $\widehat{c}_n^{(k)}$ (see [18]). If $k = 1$, then $\widehat{c}_n^{(1)} = \widehat{c}_n$ is the classical Cauchy number (see [7, 27]). The poly-Cauchy numbers of the second kind $\widehat{c}_n^{(k)}$ can be expressed in terms of the Stirling numbers of the first kind by

$$\widehat{c}_n^{(k)} = (-1)^n \sum_{m=0}^n \frac{S_1(n, m)}{(m+1)^k} \quad (n \geq 0, k \geq 1)$$

([18, Theorem 4]). The generating function of the poly-Cauchy numbers of the second kind $\widehat{c}_n^{(k)}$ is given by

$$\text{Lif}_k(-\ln(1+t)) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \widehat{c}_n^{(k)} \frac{t^n}{n!} \tag{7}$$

([18, Theorem 5]).

The poly-Cauchy numbers (of the both kinds) are extended to the poly-Cauchy polynomials (see [14]), and to the poly-Cauchy numbers with a q parameter (see [19]). The corresponding poly-Bernoulli numbers with a q parameter can be obtained in [6]. A different direction of generalizations of Cauchy numbers is about

hypergeometric Cauchy numbers (see [21]). Arithmetical and combinatorial properties including sums of products have been studied (see [20, 23, 24]).

Various kinds of q -analogues or extensions have been studied. In [17], as generalizations of the poly-Cauchy numbers of the first kind $c_n^{(k)}$ and of the second kind $\widehat{c}_n^{(k)}$, by using Jackson's q -integrals, q -analogues or extensions of the poly-Cauchy numbers of the first kind $c_{n,q}^{(k)}$ and of the second kind $\widehat{c}_{n,q}^{(k)}$ are introduced, and their properties are investigated. In [22], by using Jackson's q -integrals, the concept about q -analogues or extensions of the poly-Bernoulli polynomials $B_{n,q}^{(k)}(z)$ with a parameter were also introduced.

In this paper, by using Jackson's q -integrals, as essential generalizations of the previously known numbers and polynomials, including poly-Bernoulli numbers $B_n^{(k)}$, the poly-Cauchy numbers of the first kind $c_n^{(k)}$ and of the second kind $\widehat{c}_n^{(k)}$, we introduce the concept of q -analogues or extensions of the poly-Bernoulli polynomials $B_{n,\rho,q}^{(k)}(z)$ with a parameter, and the poly-Cauchy polynomials of the first kind $c_{n,\rho,q}^{(k)}$ and of the second kind $\widehat{c}_{n,\rho,q}^{(k)}$ with a parameter. We investigate their properties connected with the usual Stirling numbers and the weighted Stirling numbers. We also give the relations between generalized poly-Bernoulli polynomials and two kinds of generalized poly-Cauchy polynomials.

2. q -multiparameter-Cauchy Polynomials

For an n -tuple $A = (\alpha_0, \alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_{n-1})$ of real numbers, define *multiparameter Stirling numbers of the first kind* $S_1(n, m, A)$ and of the *second kind* $S_2(n, m, A)$ by

$$(t - \alpha_0)(t - \alpha_1) \cdots (t - \alpha_{n-1}) = \sum_{m=0}^n S_1(n, m, A)t^m \tag{8}$$

and

$$\sum_{m=0}^n S_2(n, m, A)(t - \alpha_0)(t - \alpha_1) \cdots (t - \alpha_{m-1}) = t^n, \tag{9}$$

respectively (cf. [7, 9, 26]). If $\alpha_i = i\rho$ ($i = 0, 1, \dots, n - 1$), then

$$\begin{aligned} S_1(n, m, (0, \rho, \dots, (n - 1)\rho)) &= (-\rho)^{n-m} S_1(n, m), \\ S_2(n, m, (0, \rho, \dots, (n - 1)\rho)) &= \rho^{n-m} S_2(n, m), \end{aligned}$$

where $S_1(n, m)$ and $S_2(n, m)$ are the (unsigned) Stirling numbers of the first kind and the Stirling numbers of the second kind, respectively.

The q -multiparameter-poly-Cauchy polynomials of the first kind can be expressed explicitly in terms of the multiparameter Stirling numbers of the first kind.

Theorem 1. For all integers n and k with $n \geq 0$ and a real number q with $0 < q < 1$, we have

$$c_{n,L,A,q}^{(k)}(z) = \sum_{m=0}^n S_1(n, m, A) \sum_{i=0}^m \binom{m}{i} \frac{(-z)^i \ell^{m-i+1}}{[m-i+1]_q^k}.$$

Proof. By definitions of (4) and (8), we have

$$\begin{aligned} c_{n,L,A,q}^{(k)}(z) &= \int_0^{\ell^{l_1}} \cdots \int_0^{\ell^{l_k}} \sum_{m=0}^n S_1(n, m, A) (x_1 \cdots x_k - z)^m d_q x_1 \cdots d_q x_k \\ &= \sum_{m=0}^n S_1(n, m, A) \sum_{i=0}^m \binom{m}{i} (-z)^{m-i} \int_0^{\ell^{l_1}} \cdots \int_0^{\ell^{l_k}} x_1^i \cdots x_k^i d_q x_1 \cdots d_q x_k \\ &= \sum_{m=0}^n S_1(n, m, A) \sum_{i=0}^m \binom{m}{i} \frac{(-z)^{m-i}}{[i+1]_q^k} \ell^{i+1} \\ &= \sum_{m=0}^n S_1(n, m, A) \sum_{i=0}^m \binom{m}{i} \frac{(-z)^i}{[m-i+1]_q^k} \ell^{m-i+1}. \end{aligned}$$

□

If $z = 0$, then we have the expression of the q -multiparameter-poly-Cauchy numbers of the first kind.

Corollary 1. For all integers n and k with $n \geq 0$ and a real number q with $0 < q < 1$, we have

$$c_{n,L,A,q}^{(k)} = \sum_{m=0}^n \frac{S_1(n, m, A) \ell^{m+1}}{[m+1]_q^k}.$$

Similarly, the q -multiparameter-poly-Cauchy polynomials of the second kind can be expressed explicitly in terms of the multiparameter Stirling numbers of the first kind. The proof is similar to that of Theorem 1 and is omitted.

Theorem 2. For all integers n and k with $n \geq 0$ and a real number q with $0 < q < 1$, we have

$$\hat{c}_{n,L,A,q}^{(k)}(z) = \sum_{m=0}^n (-1)^m S_1(n, m, A) \sum_{i=0}^m \binom{m}{i} \frac{(-z)^i \ell^{m-i+1}}{[m-i+1]_q^k}.$$

If $z = 0$, then we have the expression of the q -multiparameter-poly-Cauchy numbers of the second kind.

Corollary 2. For all integers n and k with $n \geq 0$ and a real number q with $0 < q < 1$, we have

$$\widehat{c}_{n,L,A,q}^{(k)} = \sum_{m=0}^n \frac{(-1)^m S_1(n, m, A) \ell^{m+1}}{[m+1]_q^k}.$$

There are simple relations between two kinds of q -multiparameter-poly-Cauchy polynomials.

Theorem 3. For all integers n and k with $n \geq 1$ and a real number q with $0 < q < 1$, we have

$$(-1)^n c_{n,L,A,q}^{(k)}(z) = \widehat{c}_{n,L,-A,q}^{(k)}(z), \tag{10}$$

$$(-1)^n \widehat{c}_{n,L,A,q}^{(k)}(z) = c_{n,L,-A,q}^{(k)}(z), \tag{11}$$

where $-A = (-\alpha_0, -\alpha_1, \dots, -\alpha_{n-1})$.

Proof. We shall prove identity (11). The identity (10) is proven similarly and omitted. By the definition of $\widehat{c}_{n,L,A,q}^{(k)}(z)$, we see that

$$\begin{aligned} & (-1)^n \widehat{c}_{n,L,A,q}^{(k)}(z) \\ &= (-1)^n \int_0^{l_1} \cdots \int_0^{l_k} (-x_1 \cdots x_k + z - \alpha_0) \cdots (-x_1 \cdots x_k + z - \alpha_{n-1}) d_q x_1 \cdots d_q x_k \\ &= \int_0^{l_1} \cdots \int_0^{l_k} (x_1 \cdots x_k - z + \alpha_0) \cdots (x_1 \cdots x_k - z + \alpha_{n-1}) d_q x_1 \cdots d_q x_k \\ &= c_{n,L,-A,q}^{(k)}(z). \end{aligned}$$

□

3. q -multiparameter-poly-Bernoulli Polynomials

Define the q -multiparameter-poly-Bernoulli polynomials $B_{n,L,A,q}^{(k)}(z)$ by

$$B_{n,L,A,q}^{(k)}(z) = \sum_{m=0}^n S_2(n, m, A) m! \sum_{i=0}^m \binom{m}{i} \frac{(-z)^i \ell^{m-i+1}}{[m-i+1]_q^k}. \tag{12}$$

This is a generalization of poly-Bernoulli polynomials $B_n^{(k)}(z)$, defined in [24]. If $q \rightarrow 1$, $l_1 = \cdots = l_k = 1$ and $\alpha_i = i$ ($i = 0, 1, \dots, n - 1$), then the polynomial $B_{n,L,A,q}^{(k)}(z)$ are reduced to the polynomial $B_n^{(k)}(z)$ in [24].

By putting $z = 0$ in (12), the q -multiparameter-poly-Bernoulli numbers $B_{n,L,A,q}^{(k)}$ are given by

$$B_{n,L,A,q}^{(k)} = \sum_{m=0}^n \frac{S_2(n, m, A)m!\ell^{m+1}}{[m+1]_q^k}. \tag{13}$$

Since the orthogonality relations

$$\sum_{k=i}^n S_1(n, k, A)S_2(k, i, A) = \sum_{k=i}^n S_1(k, i, A)S_2(n, k, A) = \delta_{n,i}, \tag{14}$$

where $\delta_{n,i}$ is the Kronecker's delta, we obtain the inverse relation

$$f_n = \sum_{m=0}^n S_1(n, m, A)g_m \iff g_n = \sum_{m=0}^n S_2(n, m, A)f_m. \tag{15}$$

Theorem 4. *For q -multiparameter-poly-Bernoulli and q -multiparameter-poly-Cauchy polynomials, we have*

$$\sum_{m=0}^n S_1(n, m, A)B_{m,L,A,q}^{(k)}(z) = n! \sum_{i=0}^n \binom{n}{i} \frac{(-z)^i \ell^{n-i+1}}{[n-i+1]_q^k}, \tag{16}$$

$$\sum_{m=0}^n S_2(n, m, A)c_{m,L,A,q}^{(k)}(z) = \sum_{i=0}^n \binom{n}{i} \frac{(-z)^i \ell^{n-i+1}}{[n-i+1]_q^k}, \tag{17}$$

$$\sum_{m=0}^n S_2(n, m, A)\hat{c}_{m,L,A,q}^{(k)}(z) = (-1)^n \sum_{i=0}^n \binom{n}{i} \frac{(-z)^i \ell^{n-i+1}}{[n-i+1]_q^k}. \tag{18}$$

Remark. If $q \rightarrow 1$ and $\alpha_i = i\rho$ ($i = 0, 1, \dots, n - 1$), then Theorem 4 is reduced to Theorem 3.2 in [6].

Proof. By (12), applying (15) with

$$f_m = m! \sum_{i=0}^m \binom{m}{i} \frac{(-z)^i \ell^{m-i+1}}{[m-i+1]_q^k} \quad \text{and} \quad g_n = B_{n,L,A,q}^{(k)}(z),$$

we get the identity (16). Similarly, by Theorem 1 and Theorem 2 we have the identities (17) and (18), respectively. □

If we put $z = 0$ in Theorem 4, we have the identities for appropriate numbers.

Corollary 3. *For q -multiparameter-poly-Bernoulli and q -multiparameter-poly-Cauchy*

numbers, we have

$$\sum_{m=0}^n S_1(n, m, A) B_{m,L,A,q}^{(k)} = \frac{n! \ell^{n+1}}{[n+1]_q^k}, \tag{19}$$

$$\sum_{m=0}^n S_2(n, m, A) c_{m,L,A,q}^{(k)} = \frac{\ell^{n+1}}{[n+1]_q^k}, \tag{20}$$

$$\sum_{m=0}^n S_2(n, m, A) \widehat{c}_{m,L,A,q}^{(k)} = \frac{(-1)^n \ell^{n+1}}{[n+1]_q^k}. \tag{21}$$

4. Several Relations of q -poly-Bernoulli Polynomials and q -poly-Cauchy Polynomials

Theorem 5. For any z we have

$$\begin{aligned} B_{n,L,A,q}^{(k)}(z) &= \sum_{\mu=0}^n \sum_{m=\mu}^n m! S_2(n, m, A) S_2(m, \mu, A) c_{\mu,L,A,q}^{(k)}(z), \\ B_{n,L,A,q}^{(k)}(z) &= \sum_{\mu=0}^n \sum_{m=\mu}^n (-1)^m m! S_2(n, m, A) S_2(m, \mu, A) \widehat{c}_{\mu,L,A,q}^{(k)}(z), \\ c_{n,L,A,q}^{(k)}(z) &= \sum_{\mu=0}^n \sum_{m=\mu}^n \frac{1}{m!} S_1(n, m, A) S_1(m, \mu, A) B_{\mu,L,A,q}^{(k)}(z), \\ \widehat{c}_{n,L,A,q}^{(k)}(z) &= \sum_{\mu=0}^n \sum_{m=\mu}^n \frac{(-1)^m}{m!} S_1(n, m, A) S_1(m, \mu, A) B_{\mu,L,A,q}^{(k)}(z). \end{aligned}$$

Remark. If $\rho = 1$ and $q \rightarrow 1$ and $\alpha_i = i\rho$ ($i = 0, 1, \dots, n - 1$), then Theorem 5 is reduced to Theorem 4.1 in [24]. A different generalization without Jackson's integrals is discussed in [23].

Proof. We shall prove the first and the fourth identities. The other two are proven similarly and omitted. By (17) in Theorem 4 and (12), we have

$$\begin{aligned} B_{n,L,A,q}^{(k)}(z) &= \sum_{m=0}^n S_2(n, m, A) m! \sum_{\mu=0}^m S_2(m, \mu, A) c_{\mu,L,A,q}^{(k)}(z) \\ &= \sum_{\mu=0}^n \sum_{m=\mu}^n m! S_2(n, m, A) S_2(m, \mu, A) c_{\mu,L,A,q}^{(k)}(z). \end{aligned}$$

By (16) in Theorem 4 and Theorem 2, we have

$$\begin{aligned}\widehat{c}_{n,L,A,q}^{(k)}(z) &= \sum_{m=0}^n \frac{(-1)^m}{m!} S_1(n, m, A) \sum_{\mu=0}^m S_1(m, \mu, A) B_{\mu,L,A,q}^{(k)}(z) \\ &= \sum_{\mu=0}^n \sum_{m=\mu}^n \frac{(-1)^m}{m!} S_1(n, m, A) S_1(m, \mu, A) B_{\mu,L,A,q}^{(k)}(z).\end{aligned}$$

□

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